

Research Paper Writing: Supply Chain Functions of Apple and Samsung Incorporation

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Supply Chain Functions of Apple and Samsung Incorporation

Introduction

The paper will be aimed at analyzing the competitive advantage between Samsung Incorporation and Apple Incorporation in terms of their supply chain and procurement.

Research Question

Which of the competitors is superior regarding each separate function?

Research Objectives

To explore the supply chain functions of Apple and Samsung incorporation, comparatively.

Discussion

Apple Incorporation has been pioneering and inventive while its commencement in the Smartphone industry. Apple is regarded as a successful brand not only countrywide but globally too. Their accomplishment is openly connected to the fabrication of their proficient products linked with technology and computers (Apple, 2014). Business level strategy of Samsung Group is to create differentiation in their products to gain distinctive edge amongst their competitors. The management included the creation of new products, marketing, overseas operations, and personnel development.

The main objective of Samsung Incorporation is to persuade ingenuity and discover new insights to support their customers with contentment and gratification. Presently Samsung Incorporation is fiscally steady and strives to nurture additionally in the upcoming years (Lee,

2014). The more customers will be satisfied the more they will stand amongst the leaders. The potential strategies for considerable enlargement of Samsung are reliant on the technical developments and novel modifications.

Supply Chain Functions of Apple Incorporation

In accordance to Hitt et.al (2012) the supply chain functions of Apple Incorporation are considered to be amongst the best in the industry. In relevance to the function of product, the keep on innovating their products based on their efficient suppliers. Their suppliers comprehend the demands of the company and manufactures exactly what they anticipate from them. Their inventory management is considered to be excellent because they relate it to their demand management amongst consumers. They ensure the availability of their products rather than disappointing their customers with weak inventory management. The suppliers of the Apple quote relatively fair pricing inclusive of the material as well as the labor along with the overheads. Relating to the location in terms of procurement, relates to the availability of the product associated to the keenness of the supplier (Apple, 2014).

The suppliers of Apple ensure to deliver their products on the given deadlines without any delays; in case of any mishap they are always prepared with substitute planning. This directly relates to the function of transportation as they are aware of the routes and circumstances they area accountable to deliver the products of Apple Incorporation. Verily, they are aware of the information the company provides them in accordance to which they manufacture the product with premium excellence and efficiency.

Supply Chain Functions of Samsung Incorporation

Samsung Incorporation carries a vast and complex supply chain management system which often reflects a weak part of the organization. In terms of the product, their suppliers are often confused and unable to comprehend the real demand of the company which results in failure at the very first place. After amplified supervision and guidance they are able to produce the demanded product (Lee, 2014). Unluckily, Samsung Incorporation's supply unit is unable to manage their inventories resulting in unavailability of products mainly in the category of Smartphone's and their colors.

Likewise, the availability is associated to the location and transportation of the products interconnected to the eagerness and enthusiasm of the suppliers themselves. Currently, Samsung Incorporation is working in regard to their supply chain managers and is striving to hire the experts to improve their supply chain obstacles. In accordance to Emerald Management, (2015) the supply chain unit of Samsung carries a greater room for improvement in terms of achieving the level of six sigma in supply chain efficiency.

Comparison of Apple and Samsung's Supply Chain Functions

Comparing the functions and efficiency level of both the organizations it can be depicted that Apple Incorporation carries a better position in terms of supply chain unit (Apple, 2014). They have a proper and adequate inventory management system which facilitates the customers on time based on their preferences. For example, an Apple user can easily find their desired product in Apple stores based on their prefer colors, models and even its accessories. This creates brand loyalty in their customers, generating a sense of ownership and attachment with the brand.

However, Samsung Incorporation is also a huge name but experts say that it requires a greater room of improvisation to accomplish the level of six sigma and premium excellence (Emerald Managemnt, 2015). Hence, the research question is answered relating to the fact that Apple incorporation is termed amongst the best organizations for its supply chain management and interconnected functions.

Conclusion

Therefore, it can be concluded that Apple Incorporation is amongst the leading supply chain management in the industry.

References

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